

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Running head: crBD prior and empirical processes

The limits of the constant-rate birth-death prior for phylogenetic tree topology inference

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SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE S1.

META-DATA FOR ALL 1189 INCLUDED EMPIRICAL TIME TREE TREES. TABLE INCLUDES THE PUBMED / *TIME TREE* ID, ARTICLE NAME, FIRST AUTHOR NAME, YEAR, AND DOI.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE S3.

META-DATA FOR THE 300 TIME TREE SUBSET. TABLE INCLUDES THE STUDY NAME, FIRST AUTHOR NAME, DOI, YEAR, MOLECULAR DATING METHOD, AND TREE PRIOR USED IN THE STUDY.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES S1 AND S3 ARE ATTACHED AS SEPARATE EXCEL FILES ON DRYAD AND ZENODO.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE S2.

TREE TOPOLOGY INDICES FOR BINARY TREES. TABLE INCLUDES THE INDEX NAME, DESCRIPTION, INTERPRETATION, SOFTWARE AVAILABILITY IN R, AND SOURCE.

Index	Description	Interpretation ^a	Software Availability in R	Source
(Im)balance Indices*				
Colless index, I_c	Sum of absolute differences subtended by left and right leaves of internal nodes, including the root; an aggregate imbalance value among internal nodes.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	apTreeshape (Bortolussi et al. 2006), castor (Louca and Doebeli 2018), phyloTop (Kendall et al. 2018), treebalance, (Mareike Fischer et al. 2021) treeCentrality (Chindelevitch 2019)	(Colless 1982)
Normalized Colless Index, I_c	Colless index normalized by the maximum value for a tree of that size.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	apTreeshape, castor, phyloTop, treebalance	(Heard 1992)
Colless-like indices, $\mathbb{C}_{D,f}$	Sum of the balance values of the internal nodes relative to f (f-size) and D (dissimilarity) of a tree. A generalization of the Colless index to rooted non-binary trees, with several variations.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	CollessLike (Mir et al. 2018), treebalance	(Mir et al. 2018)
Equal weights Colless index (I_2 index)	Modified Colless index that applies equal weight to all internal nodes of a tree; counteracts ‘deep’ nodes being weighted heavier in the standard I_c .	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Mooers and Heard 1997)

Total $I(I')$ index	Sum of imbalance values of all binary nodes in the tree. Imbalance values are the “ratio between the observed deviation of the larger pending subtree from the minimum value possible and the maximum deviation possible” (Fischer et al. 2021).	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Fusco and Cronk 1995; Purvis et al. 2002)
Mean/Median $I(I')$ index	Mean/median of imbalance values of all binary nodes in the tree, where imbalance values for I are defined as above.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Fusco and Cronk 1995; Purvis et al. 2002)
Sackin index	Sum of the edges from a leaf to the root for all leaves; a sum of depths on tree T.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	apTreeshape, castor, phyloTop, treebalance, treeCentrality	(Sackin 1972; Kirxpatrick and Slatkin 1993)
Normalized Sackin index	Sackin index divided by a normalization value.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	phyloTop	(Blum et al. 2006)
Total cophenetic index, Φ	Sum of the depths of the common ancestor of all pairs of leaves (i.e., sum of cophenetic values [depth of the most recent common ancestor]).	Lower values suggest greater balance.	CollessLike, TotalCopheneticIndex (Mir et al. 2013), TreeTools (Smith 2019), treebalance	(Mir et al. 2013)
B_1 index	The sum of the inverse heights of subtrees subrooted to internal nodes of a tree, excluding the root.	Higher values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Shao and Sokal 1990)
B_2 index	Measures the equitability of arriving at the leaves of a tree when starting at the root and assuming equiprobable branching at each inner vertex; it is a Shannon-Wiener information function (Fischer et al. 2021).	Higher values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Shao and Sokal 1990)
Average leaf depth	Mean of leaf depths in a tree, where depth is the number	Lower values	treebalance	(Sackin 1972;

(\bar{N})	of leaves in a pending subtree attached to each node.	suggest greater balance.		Shao and Sokal 1990)
Leaf Depth Variance (σ_N^2)	Variance of leaf depths in a tree.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Sackin 1972; Shao and Sokal 1990; M. Coronado et al. 2020)
Colijn-Plazotta rank	Recursively defined bijective mapping between rooted binary trees and the positive integers.(Fischer et al. 2021)	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treetop, treebalance	(Colijn and Plazzotta 2018; Rosenberg 2021)
J index	Number of interior nodes that are not balanced in a rooted, binary tree.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	symmeTree (Kersting and Fischer 2021), treebalance	(Rogers 1996)
Symmetry nodes index (SNI)	Number of interior nodes which are not symmetry nodes; a node is a symmetry node if its two maximal pendant subtrees are isomorphic.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	symmeTree, treebalance	(Kersting and Fischer 2021)
\hat{S} -shape statistic	Sum of the log value of all clade sizes (for all internal nodes) in a tree minus one.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance, apTreeshape, castor	(Blum and François 2006)
Maximum depth	Maximum depth of any leaf in the tree, where depth is the number of edges from a leaf to the root.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	phyloTop, treebalance	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Maximum width	Maximum number of nodes for each depth, d , in the tree.	Higher values suggest greater balance.	phyloTop, treebalance, treeCentrality	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Width-depth ratio	Ratio of the maximum width of a tree to the maximum depth.	Higher values suggest greater balance.		(Colijn and Gardy 2014)

Maximum difference in widths	Maximum difference in width values at any value for depth, d .	Higher values suggest greater balance.	phyloTop, treebalance	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Mean depth	Mean topological distance of each node, including both internal nodes and leaves, to the root.	Lower values suggest greater balance.	phyloTop, treeCentrality	(Herrada et al. 2011)
Rooted Quartet index	Balance index based on the symmetry of the evolutionary history of every set of 4 leaves; sum of symmetry values of each 4-tuple of leaves in a tree.	Higher values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Coronado et al. 2019)
Furnas rank	Ranking of trees, which occurs through the “left-light rooted ranking” system, which assigns an integer value rank to each tree with a given number of terminal nodes. Balanced trees receive larger values relative to the number of possible distinct topologies.	Higher values suggest greater balance.	treebalance	(Furnas 1984; Kirxpatrick and Slatkin 1993)
stairs/stairs1/ staircase-ness measure	The proportion of sub-trees for all vertices that are imbalanced (i.e., sub-trees where the left child contains more leaves than the right child, or vice-versa).	Lower values suggest greater balance.	treebalance, phyloTempo (Norström et al. 2012), phyloTop, treeCentrality	(Norström et al. 2012)
stairs2	The mean ratio between the number of leaves of the smaller and larger pending subtree over all inner vertices.(Fischer et al. 2021) The average of all the $\min(l,r)/\max(l,r)$ values of each sub-tree, where l and r are the number of leaves in the left and right children of a subtree.(Norström et al. 2012)	Higher values suggest greater balance.	treebalance, phyloTop, treeCentrality	(Norström et al. 2012)
Other Tree Indices				
Mean I'_{10} index	Mean $I(I')$ index for the 10 earliest nodes of a tree.			(Fusco and Cronk 1995; Purvis et al. 2002)

Number of cherries	Number of adjacent pairs of leaves with a common ancestor node.		phyloTop, ape (Paradis and Schliep 2019), treebalance, treeCentrality	(McKenzie and Steel 2000)
Normalized number of cherries	Number of cherries divided by half the number of tips in a tree.		phyloTop	(McKenzie and Steel 2000)
Modified cherry index	Number of leaves which are not in a cherry in a rooted, binary tree.			(Kersting and Fischer 2021)
Number of r -pronged nodes or r -caterpillars	Number of nodes which subtends r number of cherries, or the number of caterpillars with r number of leaves.			(Rosenberg 2006; Chindelevitch et al. 2021)
D index (weighted ℓ_1 distance)	Compares the empirical and theoretical distributions of the number of subtrees under a Yule model. Is the weighted ℓ_1 distance between the two distributions.			(Blum and François 2005)
Degree of root imbalance	The proportion of taxa found in the more diverse group (maximal pending subtree) compared to the total number of taxa from the root.			(Guyer and Slowinski 1993)
Area Per Pair (APP) index	The average distance between all pairs of leaves in a tree, where distance denotes the number of edges that connect leaves.		treebalance	(Lima et al. 2020)
IL Number	Number of internal nodes with a single tip child; equivalent to modified cherry index for rooted, binary trees.(Fischer et al. 2021)		phyloTop	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Ladder lengths	Maximum number of connected IL nodes with a single leaf descendant, divided by the total number of leaves.		phyloTop	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)

Average ladder length	Mean size of ladders in a tree.		phyloTop	(Colijn and Gardy 2014)
Maximum height	Maximum height of tips in the tree.		phyloTop, treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Maximum betweenness**	Maximum number of shortest paths that pass through a particular node.		treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Maximum closeness**	Sum of lengths of the shortest paths between one node and all other nodes (maximum thereof).		treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Average pathlength**	The average topological distance between any two nodes.		treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Diameter**	Longest possible path between two nodes in the tree.		treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)
Pitchforks	Number of substructures consisting of three tips.		phyloTop, treeCentrality	(Metzig et al. 2019)

^aThis can depend on the structure of the tree (i.e., the most balanced trees according to one index may not be the most balanced according to other indices). All indices consider caterpillar trees to be the least balanced, but the most balanced may differ (e.g., I_2 and B_1 versus rooted quartet index) (Fischer et al. 2021).

*As defined by (Fischer et al. 2021). Further derivations and details for the majority of indices can also be found within (Fischer et al. 2021).

**Centrality and general network measures, as defined by (Metzig et al. 2019).

Some metrics can be normalized based on the number of tips in the tree (e.g., IL number)

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SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE S4.

TREE TOPOLOGY INDEX LINEAR REGRESSION ESTIMATES, T-VALUES, AND P-VALUES FOR EACH INFERENCE METHOD, AS VISUALIZED IN FIGURE 4

Median <i>I</i>	Estimate	<i>t</i>-value	p-value
(Intercept)	0.777	26.527	< 0.001
Number of tips	< -0.000	-0.271	0.786
Bayesian (BD)	0.006	0.184	0.854
Bayesian (Non-BD)	-0.043	-1.055	0.292
Non-Bayesian	Ref.		

Normalized Colless	Estimate	<i>t</i>-value	p-value
(Intercept)	0.482	19.026	< 0.001
Number of tips	-0.002	-10.975	< 0.001
Bayesian (BD)	-0.053	-1.813	0.071
Bayesian (Non-BD)	-0.041	-1.153	0.250
Non-Bayesian	Ref.		

Leaf depth variance	Estimate	<i>t</i>-value	p-value
(Intercept)	4.012	4.667	< 0.001
Number of tips	0.100	15.371	< 0.001
Bayesian (BD)	0.086	0.087	0.931
Bayesian (Non-BD)	-1.087	-0.904	0.367
Non-Bayesian	Ref.		

B₂	Estimate	<i>t</i>-value	p-value
(Intercept)	2.639	30.046	< 0.001
Number of tips	0.006	9.128	< 0.001
Bayesian (BD)	0.049	0.488	0.626
Bayesian (Non-BD)	0.255	2.076	0.039
Non-Bayesian	Ref.		

stairs2	Estimate	<i>t</i>-value	p-value
(Intercept)	0.599	59.884	< 0.001
Number of tips	< 0.000	0.098	0.922
Bayesian (BD)	0.006	0.555	0.579
Bayesian (Non-BD)	0.013	0.902	0.368
Non-Bayesian	Ref.		

TREE TOPOLOGY INDEX LINEAR REGRESSION ESTIMATES, T-VALUES, AND P-VALUES FOR EACH INFERENCE METHOD, STRATIFIED BY BIRTH-DEATH PRIOR TYPE

Median <i>I</i>	Estimate	<i>t</i>-value	p-value
(Intercept)	0.776	26.524	< 0.001
Number of tips	< -0.001	-0.147	0.884
Bayesian (BD, Birth-Death)	-0.036	-0.832	0.406
Bayesian (BD, Not specified)	0.007	0.144	0.886
Bayesian (BD, Yule)	0.028	0.750	0.454
Bayesian (Non-BD)	-0.045	-1.095	0.274
Non-Bayesian	Ref.		

Normalized Colless	Estimate	<i>t</i>-value	p-value
(Intercept)	0.482	19.026	< 0.001
Number of tips	-0.002	-10.815	> 0.001
Bayesian (BD, Birth-Death)	-0.070	-1.854	0.065
Bayesian (BD, Not specified)	-0.046	-1.168	0.244
Bayesian (BD, Yule)	-0.048	-1.475	0.141
Bayesian (Non-BD)	-0.040	-1.119	0.264
Non-Bayesian	Ref.		

Leaf depth variance	Estimate	<i>t</i>-value	p-value
(Intercept)	3.997	4.681	< 0.001
Number of tips	0.100	15.467	< 0.001
Bayesian (BD, Birth-Death)	-1.446	-1.135	0.257
Bayesian (BD, Not specified)	0.315	0.236	0.814
Bayesian (BD, Yule)	1.032	0.946	0.345
Bayesian (Non-BD)	-1.494	-1.244	0.214
Non-Bayesian	Ref.		

B₂	Estimate	<i>t</i>-value	p-value
(Intercept)	2.642	29.972	< 0.001
Number of tips	0.006	8.927	< 0.001
Bayesian (BD, Birth-Death)	0.132	1.004	0.316
Bayesian (BD, Not specified)	-0.010	-0.074	0.941
Bayesian (BD, Yule)	0.049	0.432	0.666
Bayesian (Non-BD)	0.239	1.927	0.055
Non-Bayesian	Ref.		

stairs2	Estimate	<i>t</i>-value	p-value
(Intercept)	0.599	59.707	< 0.001
Number of tips	< 0.001	0.059	0.953
Bayesian (BD, Birth-Death)	0.010	0.683	0.495
Bayesian (BD, Not specified)	0.010	0.637	0.525
Bayesian (BD, Yule)	0.003	0.241	0.810
Bayesian (Non-BD)	0.013	0.886	0.376
Non-Bayesian	Ref.		

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE S5.

EFFECTIVE SAMPLE SIZE (ESS) VALUES FOR EACH OF THE 100 INFERRED REVBayES TREES FOR ALL THREE SUBSTITUTION RATES (0.5, 0.05, 0.005).

Rate = 0.5		Rate = 0.05		Rate = 0.005	
File name	ESS*	File name	ESS*	File name	ESS*
sequence rate2 1.fasta.log	1777	sequence rate3 1.fasta.log	2532	sequence rate4 1.fasta.log	2386
sequence rate2 10.fasta.log	1725	sequence rate3 10.fasta.log	1411	sequence rate4 10.fasta.log	3257
sequence rate2 100.fasta.log	1509	sequence rate3 100.fasta.log	2555	sequence rate4 100.fasta.log	3053
sequence rate2 11.fasta.log	1679	sequence rate3 11.fasta.log	2269	sequence rate4 11.fasta.log	3942
sequence rate2 12.fasta.log	1433	sequence rate3 12.fasta.log	2377	sequence rate4 12.fasta.log	3425
sequence rate2 13.fasta.log	1591	sequence rate3 13.fasta.log	1876	sequence rate4 13.fasta.log	2413
sequence rate2 14.fasta.log	1010	sequence rate3 14.fasta.log	2693	sequence rate4 14.fasta.log	2337
sequence rate2 15.fasta.log	1474	sequence rate3 15.fasta.log	2747	sequence rate4 15.fasta.log	3758
sequence rate2 16.fasta.log	1664	sequence rate3 16.fasta.log	2304	sequence rate4 16.fasta.log	2661
sequence rate2 17.fasta.log	1590	sequence rate3 17.fasta.log	2459	sequence rate4 17.fasta.log	3430
sequence rate2 18.fasta.log	1570	sequence rate3 18.fasta.log	2563	sequence rate4 18.fasta.log	3755
sequence rate2 19.fasta.log	1616	sequence rate3 19.fasta.log	1364	sequence rate4 19.fasta.log	2255
sequence rate2 2.fasta.log	1818	sequence rate3 2.fasta.log	2971	sequence rate4 2.fasta.log	3127
sequence rate2 20.fasta.log	1358	sequence rate3 20.fasta.log	1902	sequence rate4 20.fasta.log	1651
sequence rate2 21.fasta.log	1573	sequence rate3 21.fasta.log	2362	sequence rate4 21.fasta.log	3429
sequence rate2 22.fasta.log	1352	sequence rate3 22.fasta.log	2180	sequence rate4 22.fasta.log	3294
sequence rate2 23.fasta.log	1132	sequence rate3 23.fasta.log	1647	sequence rate4 23.fasta.log	2798
sequence rate2 24.fasta.log	1769	sequence rate3 24.fasta.log	2994	sequence rate4 24.fasta.log	4002
sequence rate2 25.fasta.log	1724	sequence rate3 25.fasta.log	1896	sequence rate4 25.fasta.log	2253
sequence rate2 26.fasta.log	1458	sequence rate3 26.fasta.log	1674	sequence rate4 26.fasta.log	2160
sequence rate2 27.fasta.log	1757	sequence rate3 27.fasta.log	1438	sequence rate4 27.fasta.log	2375
sequence rate2 28.fasta.log	1636	sequence rate3 28.fasta.log	2191	sequence rate4 28.fasta.log	3387
sequence rate2 29.fasta.log	1172	sequence rate3 29.fasta.log	2582	sequence rate4 29.fasta.log	2791

sequence_rate2_3.fasta.log	1653	sequence_rate3_3.fasta.log	3393	sequence_rate4_3.fasta.log	3676
sequence_rate2_30.fasta.log	2030	sequence_rate3_30.fasta.log	2369	sequence_rate4_30.fasta.log	2813
sequence_rate2_31.fasta.log	1926	sequence_rate3_31.fasta.log	1775	sequence_rate4_31.fasta.log	1922
sequence_rate2_32.fasta.log	1715	sequence_rate3_32.fasta.log	1954	sequence_rate4_32.fasta.log	2809
sequence_rate2_33.fasta.log	1330	sequence_rate3_33.fasta.log	2109	sequence_rate4_33.fasta.log	2721
sequence_rate2_34.fasta.log	1316	sequence_rate3_34.fasta.log	2253	sequence_rate4_34.fasta.log	2333
sequence_rate2_35.fasta.log	1217	sequence_rate3_35.fasta.log	1364	sequence_rate4_35.fasta.log	3362
sequence_rate2_36.fasta.log	1419	sequence_rate3_36.fasta.log	2272	sequence_rate4_36.fasta.log	3012
sequence_rate2_37.fasta.log	1448	sequence_rate3_37.fasta.log	3060	sequence_rate4_37.fasta.log	2832
sequence_rate2_38.fasta.log	1388	sequence_rate3_38.fasta.log	2289	sequence_rate4_38.fasta.log	3135
sequence_rate2_39.fasta.log	1595	sequence_rate3_39.fasta.log	2383	sequence_rate4_39.fasta.log	2596
sequence_rate2_4.fasta.log	1785	sequence_rate3_4.fasta.log	3134	sequence_rate4_4.fasta.log	3425
sequence_rate2_40.fasta.log	1012	sequence_rate3_40.fasta.log	2448	sequence_rate4_40.fasta.log	2747
sequence_rate2_41.fasta.log	1818	sequence_rate3_41.fasta.log	3017	sequence_rate4_41.fasta.log	3549
sequence_rate2_42.fasta.log	1668	sequence_rate3_42.fasta.log	2306	sequence_rate4_42.fasta.log	3465
sequence_rate2_43.fasta.log	1474	sequence_rate3_43.fasta.log	2816	sequence_rate4_43.fasta.log	3531
sequence_rate2_44.fasta.log	1334	sequence_rate3_44.fasta.log	2410	sequence_rate4_44.fasta.log	2958
sequence_rate2_45.fasta.log	1431	sequence_rate3_45.fasta.log	1778	sequence_rate4_45.fasta.log	3588
sequence_rate2_46.fasta.log	1530	sequence_rate3_46.fasta.log	2328	sequence_rate4_46.fasta.log	3969
sequence_rate2_47.fasta.log	1433	sequence_rate3_47.fasta.log	2111	sequence_rate4_47.fasta.log	3241
sequence_rate2_48.fasta.log	1087	sequence_rate3_48.fasta.log	1502	sequence_rate4_48.fasta.log	2936
sequence_rate2_49.fasta.log	1572	sequence_rate3_49.fasta.log	3039	sequence_rate4_49.fasta.log	3244
sequence_rate2_5.fasta.log	1728	sequence_rate3_5.fasta.log	2920	sequence_rate4_5.fasta.log	3175
sequence_rate2_50.fasta.log	1163	sequence_rate3_50.fasta.log	1744	sequence_rate4_50.fasta.log	2233
sequence_rate2_51.fasta.log	1443	sequence_rate3_51.fasta.log	2963	sequence_rate4_51.fasta.log	2957
sequence_rate2_52.fasta.log	1571	sequence_rate3_52.fasta.log	2404	sequence_rate4_52.fasta.log	2125
sequence_rate2_53.fasta.log	1634	sequence_rate3_53.fasta.log	2633	sequence_rate4_53.fasta.log	3180
sequence_rate2_54.fasta.log	1730	sequence_rate3_54.fasta.log	2553	sequence_rate4_54.fasta.log	2509
sequence_rate2_55.fasta.log	944	sequence_rate3_55.fasta.log	1217	sequence_rate4_55.fasta.log	1907

sequence_rate2_56.fasta.log	1228	sequence_rate3_56.fasta.log	2114	sequence_rate4_56.fasta.log	3365
sequence_rate2_57.fasta.log	1747	sequence_rate3_57.fasta.log	2046	sequence_rate4_57.fasta.log	3308
sequence_rate2_58.fasta.log	2177	sequence_rate3_58.fasta.log	1698	sequence_rate4_58.fasta.log	1247
sequence_rate2_59.fasta.log	1463	sequence_rate3_59.fasta.log	2480	sequence_rate4_59.fasta.log	3260
sequence_rate2_6.fasta.log	2472	sequence_rate3_6.fasta.log	1680	sequence_rate4_6.fasta.log	2135
sequence_rate2_60.fasta.log	1525	sequence_rate3_60.fasta.log	2509	sequence_rate4_60.fasta.log	1942
sequence_rate2_61.fasta.log	1626	sequence_rate3_61.fasta.log	2130	sequence_rate4_61.fasta.log	3082
sequence_rate2_62.fasta.log	1815	sequence_rate3_62.fasta.log	2677	sequence_rate4_62.fasta.log	3058
sequence_rate2_63.fasta.log	1500	sequence_rate3_63.fasta.log	2936	sequence_rate4_63.fasta.log	3152
sequence_rate2_64.fasta.log	1674	sequence_rate3_64.fasta.log	2401	sequence_rate4_64.fasta.log	3589
sequence_rate2_65.fasta.log	1801	sequence_rate3_65.fasta.log	2406	sequence_rate4_65.fasta.log	3270
sequence_rate2_66.fasta.log	1556	sequence_rate3_66.fasta.log	1664	sequence_rate4_66.fasta.log	3793
sequence_rate2_67.fasta.log	1614	sequence_rate3_67.fasta.log	2133	sequence_rate4_67.fasta.log	1958
sequence_rate2_68.fasta.log	1369	sequence_rate3_68.fasta.log	2381	sequence_rate4_68.fasta.log	3130
sequence_rate2_69.fasta.log	942	sequence_rate3_69.fasta.log	1899	sequence_rate4_69.fasta.log	2131
sequence_rate2_7.fasta.log	1630	sequence_rate3_7.fasta.log	3055	sequence_rate4_7.fasta.log	3017
sequence_rate2_70.fasta.log	2232	sequence_rate3_70.fasta.log	1823	sequence_rate4_70.fasta.log	2853
sequence_rate2_71.fasta.log	1404	sequence_rate3_71.fasta.log	2523	sequence_rate4_71.fasta.log	3643
sequence_rate2_72.fasta.log	1209	sequence_rate3_72.fasta.log	2650	sequence_rate4_72.fasta.log	2755
sequence_rate2_73.fasta.log	1242	sequence_rate3_73.fasta.log	1296	sequence_rate4_73.fasta.log	866
sequence_rate2_74.fasta.log	1044	sequence_rate3_74.fasta.log	1486	sequence_rate4_74.fasta.log	1876
sequence_rate2_75.fasta.log	1668	sequence_rate3_75.fasta.log	1750	sequence_rate4_75.fasta.log	2055
sequence_rate2_76.fasta.log	2152	sequence_rate3_76.fasta.log	1502	sequence_rate4_76.fasta.log	1057
sequence_rate2_77.fasta.log	1170	sequence_rate3_77.fasta.log	2042	sequence_rate4_77.fasta.log	2551
sequence_rate2_78.fasta.log	1324	sequence_rate3_78.fasta.log	2123	sequence_rate4_78.fasta.log	2675
sequence_rate2_79.fasta.log	1067	sequence_rate3_79.fasta.log	1772	sequence_rate4_79.fasta.log	3084
sequence_rate2_8.fasta.log	1773	sequence_rate3_8.fasta.log	2396	sequence_rate4_8.fasta.log	2538
sequence_rate2_80.fasta.log	1327	sequence_rate3_80.fasta.log	2492	sequence_rate4_80.fasta.log	2768
sequence_rate2_81.fasta.log	1506	sequence_rate3_81.fasta.log	2072	sequence_rate4_81.fasta.log	4040

sequence_rate2_82.fasta.log	1218	sequence_rate3_82.fasta.log	2258	sequence_rate4_82.fasta.log	1540
sequence_rate2_83.fasta.log	2159	sequence_rate3_83.fasta.log	2066	sequence_rate4_83.fasta.log	3248
sequence_rate2_84.fasta.log	1333	sequence_rate3_84.fasta.log	1854	sequence_rate4_84.fasta.log	2220
sequence_rate2_85.fasta.log	1224	sequence_rate3_85.fasta.log	1961	sequence_rate4_85.fasta.log	2369
sequence_rate2_86.fasta.log	1330	sequence_rate3_86.fasta.log	1795	sequence_rate4_86.fasta.log	2064
sequence_rate2_87.fasta.log	1186	sequence_rate3_87.fasta.log	1809	sequence_rate4_87.fasta.log	2164
sequence_rate2_88.fasta.log	766	sequence_rate3_88.fasta.log	1633	sequence_rate4_88.fasta.log	2852
sequence_rate2_89.fasta.log	1363	sequence_rate3_89.fasta.log	2127	sequence_rate4_89.fasta.log	3405
sequence_rate2_9.fasta.log	1429	sequence_rate3_9.fasta.log	2624	sequence_rate4_9.fasta.log	3012
sequence_rate2_90.fasta.log	1214	sequence_rate3_90.fasta.log	1697	sequence_rate4_90.fasta.log	3006
sequence_rate2_91.fasta.log	1489	sequence_rate3_91.fasta.log	1953	sequence_rate4_91.fasta.log	2734
sequence_rate2_92.fasta.log	1137	sequence_rate3_92.fasta.log	1206	sequence_rate4_92.fasta.log	3489
sequence_rate2_93.fasta.log	1563	sequence_rate3_93.fasta.log	2504	sequence_rate4_93.fasta.log	3817
sequence_rate2_94.fasta.log	1181	sequence_rate3_94.fasta.log	2339	sequence_rate4_94.fasta.log	3235
sequence_rate2_95.fasta.log	1413	sequence_rate3_95.fasta.log	2140	sequence_rate4_95.fasta.log	2852
sequence_rate2_96.fasta.log	1489	sequence_rate3_96.fasta.log	2279	sequence_rate4_96.fasta.log	1695
sequence_rate2_97.fasta.log	1572	sequence_rate3_97.fasta.log	2533	sequence_rate4_97.fasta.log	2865
sequence_rate2_98.fasta.log	899	sequence_rate3_98.fasta.log	2025	sequence_rate4_98.fasta.log	2082
sequence_rate2_99.fasta.log	1773	sequence_rate3_99.fasta.log	2751	sequence_rate4_99.fasta.log	3557

*ESS calculated using the `effectiveSize()` function in *coda* (version 0.19-4) (Plummer et al. 2006); value rounded to the nearest 1
Code to calculate the ESS values for each inferred tree can be found on Zenodo.

Plummer M., Best N., Cowles K., Vines K. 2006. CODA: convergence diagnosis and output analysis for MCMC.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE S1.

Differences between the realized Wilcoxon (Mann-Whitney) U statistic value and the expected U value, including corresponding p-values, for each index among trees without potential outgroups ($n = 706$ trees). Dotted line represents a Bonferroni-corrected p-value. Trees with potential outgroups were defined as those where the longest pendant edge was equal to the height of the tree.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE S2.

Z-SCORE DISTRIBUTIONS FOR ALL TREE TOPOLOGY INDICES. DOTTED LINES DENOTE THE SAMPLE MEAN.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE S3.

BOX PLOTS FOR THE TOP FIVE INDICES FOR IQ-TREE 2 AND REVBayES TREES, STRATIFIED BY RATE: A) 0.5, B) 0.05, C) 0.005.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE S4.

Density plots for the index values for inferred simulated trees, where the simulated trees are based on the ML estimates from the initial empirical dataset. Trees with ≥ 10 leaves were included to avoid including extreme values due to small tree sizes, resulting in $n=1,000,300$ trees (corresponding to 1,000 simulations for each of $n=1,003$ trees with ≥ 10 leaves). The five indices are mean I , median I , normalized Colless, I_2 , and the normalized Sackin index, all of which take values between 0 and 1 and can therefore be easily interpreted from an (im)balance perspective. The results suggest that the most highly imbalanced or balanced trees are unlikely under the crBD prior.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE S5.

Density plots for each index (Imbalance indices: normalized Colless index, median I, leaf depth variance; Balance indices: B₂ index, stairs2) with rows showing the simulation substitution rates. The prior values are derived from simulated trees, where the best crBD parameters were inferred from the 100 imbalanced empirical trees. One thousand crBD trees were then simulated for each set of crBD parameters (where $\rho = 1$), whereafter index values were calculated. The full posterior distribution represents the full post-burn-in posterior set of trees, derived from the Bayesian inference process for each of the 100 inferred maximum clade credibility (MCC) RevBayes trees.